

Induction of Life molecules on the earth's metal-liquid-ionosphere system by Rotating Urey-Miller clouds in Abraham Loeb's theory

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Abstract:

Recently, Abraham Loeb has found that when temperature of the early universe with 7-10 million years old, was between 273-373 K, heavy atoms like carbon, nitrogen, hydrogen and oxygen were formed, combined with each other and produced molecules of life like water, Amino Acids and DNA/RNAs bases. Now, the question arises that how this theory could describe the process of formation of life molecules on the earth? To response this question, we suggest two models. In first model, molecules of life which are produced within a young universe join to each other and form a cosmic cloud. The process of formation of this cloud is similar to process of formation of amino acids in the Urey-Miller system. Then, this Urey-Miller cloud explodes and several smaller clouds are emerged. Each new cloud is compacted and forms the core of planets and stars. Because of compaction, molecules of life interact with each other, produce new atoms and form inner metal core and outer liquid layer. The memory of initial life remains within the liquid/metal layer and this system using metal core as sender\receiver antenna, send some life waves into medium. These waves are taken by atoms and electrons in ionosphere part of atmosphere and transmitted into carbonic, nitric and water molecules. Consequently, these molecules combine with each other and form molecules of life on the surface of earth. This model is in agreement with observations. In this model, number of stored life molecules within the initial cloud is a constant and as a result, multiplying number of creatures and their genetic molecules on the earth should be a constant. Thus, as we observe in the history of life, by passing time and increasing number of creatures, their size should be reduced. In second model, a cloud of life molecules were formed in the early universe. This cloud sends some waves from a side of universe and these waves are taken by metal core of earth. In fact, metal core of earth acts as the receiver/sender antenna and transmits these waves to ionosphere and ions within atmosphere.

Then, these charges act as second antenna and give a plan for designing life molecules to carbon, nitrogen, oxygen and molecules of water on the surface of the earth.

Keywords: Biology; Cosmology; Earth; Urey-Miller; Life; Universe

Introduction

Around 7 years ago, a known scientist, Abraham Loeb has discussed that 7-10 million years after big bang, thermal conditions of our universe became suitable for the combinations of heavy atoms like carbon and nitrogen and formation of life molecules [1]. This model confirms the results in the Urey-Miller experiment [2]. In Urey-Miller system, water became warm and its molecules begin vaporizing and combining with CH_4 , H_2 , NH_3 and some other molecules. In this system, two electrodes produced a current which radiated some strong electromagnetic waves and then, the system became cooled. After a period of time, life molecules like amino acids were created [2,3]. Until now, many researchers have studied this subject. For example, some scientists have indicated that unless habitability around low mass stars is suppressed, life is most likely to be produced near stars ten trillion years from now [4]. In another paper, investigators have shown that high abundances of water vapor could be produced in extremely low metallicity partially shielded gas during the epoch of first metal enrichment of the interstellar medium of galaxies at high redshifts [5]. In other research, scientists have considered the probability for planet creation in the carbon-rich protoplanetary discs of carbon-enhanced metal-poor (CEMP) stars, possible relics of the early Universe [6]. In other work, to discover some signatures of life, investigators have explored sources of directed energy systems such as those now becoming technologically feasible on Earth [7]. In another investigation, it has been argued that embedding parameters like habitability ones, into greater ecological models with several trophic models, make a clear bridge between the astrobiological and ecological approaches of quantitative habitability [8]. Motivated by these researches and using Urey-Miller experiments, we will build a bridge between the habitable epoch of the early Universe and the origin of life on the earth. To this aim, we suggest two scenarios and discuss favorites in each one.

Formation of planets and stars from cosmic Urey-Miller clouds

According to Abraham Loeb theory, when universe had around 7-10 million years old, its temperature was between 273-373 K. This temperature lets to heavy atoms like carbons, oxygen, nitrogen and hydrogen to combine with each other and form molecules of life like amino acids and hexagonal/pentagonal molecules of

(Cytosine, Thymine, Guanine and Adenine). In fact, the early universe is similar to Urey-Miller system which its electrodes are replaced by cosmic waves. In this system, molecules of life could join to each other and form a cosmic cloud. This cloud could rotate, explode and some new child clouds are emerged. These clouds may be the origin of planets and stars (See figure 1). We can calculate the approximate energy of this cloud. To this aim, we should know approximate values of atomic and molecular masses. We have:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Hydrogen mass} &\approx 1.6 \times 10^{-27} \text{ kg} \\
 \text{Carbon mass} &\approx 19 \times 10^{-27} \text{ kg} \\
 \text{Oxygen mass} &\approx 26 \times 10^{-27} \text{ kg} \\
 \text{Nitrogen mass} &\approx 23 \times 10^{-27} \text{ kg} \\
 \text{Cytosine mass} &\approx 111 \times 10^{-27} \text{ kg} \\
 \text{Thymine mass} &\approx 126 \times 10^{-27} \text{ kg} \\
 \text{Adenine mass} &\approx 135 \times 10^{-27} \text{ kg} \\
 \text{Guanine mass} &\approx 151 \times 10^{-27} \text{ kg} \\
 \text{Iron mass} &\approx 92 \times 10^{-27} \text{ kg}
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

When, atoms join to each other and form a molecule, the mass of system is reduced and some amounts of energy become free. For a rotating Urey-Miller cloud with the radius around 50000 light years, we can obtain:

$$E_{\text{formation}} = [\text{Mass (18Carbon + 4Oxygen + 15Nitrogen + 13Hydrogen)} - \text{Mass (Cytosine + Thymine + Adenine + Guanine)}] (\text{number of molecules in each meter}) \times \pi \times (\text{radius of life cloud})^2 (\text{velocity of light})^2 \approx 10^{44} \text{ J} \tag{2}$$

Where we have used:

$$\begin{aligned}
 1 \text{ year} &= 3153600 \text{ s} \\
 \text{Velocity of light} &= 3 \times 10^8
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Radius of cloud} \geq 50000 \text{ years of light} \geq (50000) (3)(10^8)(31536000) \geq 10^{21} \text{ m} \tag{3}$$

Above energy could be carried by some cosmic waves which their numbers could be obtained from below equation:

$$E_{\text{life waves}} \approx E_{\text{formation}} \approx 10^{44} \text{ J} \approx N_{\text{radiate}} h \nu_{\text{cosmic}} \rightarrow N_{\text{radiate}} \nu_{\text{cosmic}} \approx 10^{78}$$

$$v_{\text{cosmic}} \approx 10^{26} \rightarrow N_{\text{radiate}} \approx 10^{52} \quad (4)$$

These huge amounts of waves could cause to rotation of this cloud and its explosion. Consequently, some new child clouds with smaller sizes are emerged. These clouds could be the origin of the earth's and other planet and star's cores. However, the question arises that why the observations predict the metal core for earth? To answer, we calculate the needed energy for converting life molecules to iron ones within a earth's core :

$$E_{\text{convert}} \approx [\text{Mass (Cytosine +Thymine + Adenine+Guanine) -Mass (4Iron molecules)}]^2 (\text{number of molecules in each meter}) \times \pi \times (\text{radius of core})^2 ((\text{velocity of light})^2) \approx 10^6 \text{ J} \quad (5)$$

This energy is smaller than the radiated energy of a cloud:

$$E_{\text{convert}} \leq E_{\text{life waves}} \quad (6)$$

Thus, radiated waves from a cloud make a pressure on the separate clouds and cause that their molecules convert to irons and other one. However, some life molecules remain within the core or layers around it. In these conditions, hot core acts like an antenna and send some life waves to atmosphere and medium. Number of cosmic waves which are radiated by this metal core can be obtained from below equation.

$$E_{\text{convert}} \approx N_{\text{wave-core}} h v_{\text{cosmic}} \rightarrow N_{\text{wave-core}} v_{\text{cosmic}} \approx 10^{40} \\ v_{\text{cosmic}} \geq 10^{20} - 10^{26} \rightarrow N_{\text{wave-core}} \approx 10^{14} - 10^{20} \quad (7)$$

where $N_{\text{wave-core}}$ is the number of radiated waves with frequencies between $10^{20} - 10^{26}$ by core. Some of these waves are absorbed by crust and other layers of earth, lose their energy and move with lower frequencies. We get:

$$\text{Number of waves in each point of ionosphere} = (\text{Total number of radiated waves from core}) \gamma_{\text{earth-core}} (r_{\text{earth}} - r_{\text{core}})^{-2} \beta_{\text{ionosphere-earth}} (r_{\text{ionosphere}} - r_{\text{earth}})^{-2} \approx 10 - 10^4$$

$$v_{\text{LIFE}} \approx \leq (10^{20} - 10^{26}) \gamma_{\text{earth-core}} (r_{\text{earth}} - r_{\text{core}})^{-2} \beta_{\text{ionosphere-earth}} (r_{\text{ionosphere}} - r_{\text{earth}})^{-2} \approx \leq 10^7 - 10^{10} \text{ Hz} \quad (8)$$

where $\gamma_{\text{earth-core}}$ is the absorption factor within layers of earth and $\beta_{\text{ionosphere-earth}}$ is the absorption factor within the atmosphere layers. Above equation shows that

observed frequencies for life waves is approximately within the range of radio frequencies and number of waves in each point could be between 10 to 10000 waves. These frequencies and number of waves are in agreement with temperature of earth:

$$\begin{aligned} E &= K T = N_{\text{each point of ionosphere}} h \nu_{\text{LIFE}} \rightarrow N_{\text{each point of ionosphere}} \nu_{\text{LIFE}} \approx 10^{13} \\ \rightarrow N_{\text{each point of ionosphere}} &\approx \leq 10^3 \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Thus, the earth's core may be a part of a Urey-Miller cosmic cloud which its life molecules experience a pressure from cosmic waves and convert to irons and other metals. This core sends some life waves to atmosphere. These waves are reflected by ionosphere to the surface of earth. Then, they force into heavy atoms like carbons, nitrogen, hydrogen and oxygen to build molecules of life (See figure 1).

Now, we can introduce a new law for number of molecules of life.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Number of molecules of life on the earth} &\approx \leq \text{Number of molecules of life} \\ \text{within the child Urey-Miller cloud} &= \text{constant} \\ \rightarrow \text{Number of creatures} \times \text{number of life molecules in each creature} &= \\ \text{constant} & \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Above law indicates that by passing time and increasing number of creatures on the earth, their size should be reduced and by this, total number of life molecules tends to a constant number. For this reason, we observe that initial creatures like dinosaurs were so much big and present creatures like lizards are so much small.

Fig 1: Emergence of planets from rotating Urey-Miller clouds

Exchanging life waves between Urey-Miller clouds and the earth's core

In this section, we propose second scenario for the emergence of life on the earth. In this scenario, earth isn't formed from parts of Urey-Miller cloud and like each planet in known theories; it could be separated from stars like sun or usual cosmic clouds. But, in this model, Urey-Miller cloud exchange waves with the earth and induce life in it. In these conditions, core of the earth acts like the sender/receiver life waves and has the main role in the formation of life on the earth (See figure 2). In previous section, we have calculated the radiated energy by Urey-Miller cloud:

$$E_{\text{life waves},0} \approx 10^{44} \text{ J} \quad (11)$$

All of these energies couldn't be taken by earth. They could become speared within the space and only a minor of it may be taken by the core. We suppose that the Urey-Miller cloud has approximately billion light years distance from earth:

$$\text{Distance to earth} \approx (10^9 \text{ years of light}) (3)(10^8)(31536000) \geq 10^{26} \text{ m} \quad (12)$$

For this distance, the earth takes below amount of radiated life energies:

$$E_{\text{life waves to earth}} = E_{\text{life waves},0} (\text{Distance to earth})^{-1} \approx \leq 10^{18} \quad (13)$$

If we assume that frequencies of life waves be equal to frequencies of cosmic waves, we can obtain their numbers:

$$E_{\text{life waves to earth}} = N h \nu_{\text{cosmic}} \rightarrow N \nu_{\text{cosmic}} \approx 10^{52}$$

$$E_{\text{each point of core}} \approx E_{\text{life waves},0} (2\pi r_{\text{core}})^{-1} \approx \leq 10^{12} = N h \nu_{\text{cosmic}} \rightarrow N \nu_{\text{cosmic}} \approx \leq 10^{46}$$

$$\nu_{\text{cosmic}} \geq 10^{20} - 10^{26} \rightarrow N \approx 10^{20} - 10^{26} \quad (14)$$

These number of waves were taken in 10 billion years. Thus, to obtain the number of waves in each seconds, we write:

$$\text{Number of waves in each second} \approx (\text{Number of total wave})(\text{number of years})^{-1} (\text{number of seconds in each year})^{-1} \approx 10^3 - 10^9 \quad (15)$$

Above equation shows that number of life waves which are taken by the earth could change between 1000 to billion. Maybe, the early earth took more number of waves, for example billion ones, however, present earth only take 1000 waves in each seconds. These waves could be taken by the metal core of earth. Then, this

core reflect waves to atmosphere. However, some layers of the earth and atmosphere absorb most of this energy and consequently, frequency is decreased:

$$\nu_{LIFE} \approx (10^{20}-10^{26}) \delta_{\text{earth-layer}} (r_{\text{earth}} - r_{\text{core}})^{-2} \chi_{\text{atmosphere}} (r_{\text{ionosphere}} - r_{\text{earth}})^{-2} \approx 10^6 - 10^{11} \text{ Hz} \quad (16)$$

where $\delta_{\text{earth-layer}} / \chi_{\text{atmosphere}}$ are absorption factors within the layers of earth and atmosphere. These frequencies are in the range of radio waves. However, their shapes should be different. We should consider the shape of waves which are radiated by earth. If one finds some hexagonal/pentagonal waves, means that earth's core emits life waves and this model works (See figure 2).

Fig 2. Exchanging life waves between Urey-Miller clouds and the earth's core

Conclusion:

In this paper, we have built a bridge between life molecules in the Abraham Loeb theory with the process of emergence of life on the earth. We have shown that around 7-10 million years after big bang, at temperature between 273-313 K, carbon, nitrogen, oxygen and some other heavy atoms interact with each other and cosmic waves and produce molecules of life like amino acids and DNA/RNA bases. In fact, the early universe acts like a Urey-Miller system and cosmic waves

act like the waves which are produced by electrodes. Within the early universe, similar to Urey-Miller system, molecules of life join to each other and form a cosmic cloud. This cloud could explode into several parts and each part forms the center of a planet or star. At this point, we can suggest two assumptions. In one assumption, the small cloud is compacted, molecules are broken and iron and liquid molecules within the inner layers of earth are emerged. Liquids/Irons have the memory of life and by using metal antenna within the core, send some life waves to ionosphere and induce life on the surface of the earth. In second assumption, Urey-Miller clouds which were formed in the early universe, send life waves and these waves were taken by metal core of earth. Then, metal core sends these waves to ionosphere and let ions in this system to reflect waves and force on carbon, nitrogen, oxygen and other atoms on the earth's surface to build life molecules.

References:

[1] Loeb Abraham, The habitable epoch of the early Universe, International Journal of Astrobiology 13 (4): 337–339 (2014)
doi:10.1017/S1473550414000196.

[2] Miller, Stanley L.; Harold C. Urey (1959). "Organic Compound Synthesis on the Primitive Earth". Science. 130 (3370): 245–51. Bibcode:1959Sci...130..245M.
doi:10.1126/science.130.3370.245.

[3] Miller, Stanley L. (1953). "Production of Amino Acids Under Possible Primitive Earth Conditions" . Science. 117 (3046): 528–9.
Bibcode:1953Sci...117..528M. doi:10.1126/science.117.3046.528

[4] Loeb A, Batistab Rafael A., Sloanb David, Relative likelihood for life as a function of cosmic time, Journal of Cosmology and Astroparticle Physics, Volume 2016, August 2016, https://doi.org/10.1088/1475-7516/2016/08/040.

[5] Bialy S, Sternberg A, Loeb A 2015, WATER FORMATION DURING THE EPOCH OF FIRST METAL ENRICHMENT , ApJL 804 L29. https://doi.org/10.1088/2041-8205/804/2/L29

[6] Natalie Mashian, Abraham Loeb, CEMP stars: possible hosts to carbon planets in the early Universe, Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society,

Volume 460, Issue 3, 11 August 2016, Pages 2482–2491,
<https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stw1037>.

[7] Lubin P, The search for directed intelligence, REACH
Volume 1, March 2016, Pages 20-45.

[8] Cardenas R., Nodarse-Zulueta R., Perez N., Avila-Alonso D., Martin O. (2019)
On the Quantification of Habitability: Current Approaches. In: Cárdenas R.,
Mochalov V., Parra O., Martin O. (eds) Proceedings of the 2nd International
Conference on BioGeoSciences. BG 2017. Springer, Cham.
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-04233-2_1